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4 **Impact of Assimilating High-Resolution Atmospheric Motion Vectors on**
5 **Convective Scale Short-Term Forecasts. Part II: Assimilation Experiments of**
6 **GOES-16 Satellite Derived Winds**

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21 **Key points:**

- 22 • GOES-R derived AMV product has the potential to benefit convective scale data
23 assimilation and forecasts.
- 24 • The impact of assimilating GOES-R derived AMVs on short-range severe
25 thunderstorm forecasts is evaluated.
- 26 • It is demonstrated that the short-range forecasts of the three severe weather events
27 are all improved when assimilating the AMV data.

Abstract

29

30 Building on the results from the observing system simulation experiments
31 (OSSEs) in Part I, this study investigates the impact of assimilating Geostationary
32 Operational Environmental Satellites – 16 (GOES-16) derived Atmospheric Motion
33 Vector (AMV) data on the convective-scale numerical weather prediction (NWP) by
34 using the National Severe Storms Laboratory (NSSL) three-dimensional variational
35 (3DVAR) data assimilation system. The benefit of the AMV data assimilation (DA) to
36 short-term severe weather forecasts is assessed with three high-impact weather events
37 that occurred in spring 2018 and 2019 over the Great Plains of the United States. The
38 results show that the wind and equivalent potential temperature fields associated with
39 the storm environment and the nearby ongoing convection are improved by the AMV
40 DA, which yields better simulation of the boundaries and the subsequent forecasts of
41 storm evolution. For the quasi-linear or mesoscale convective system, the assimilation
42 of AMVs has a positive impact on the 0–3 h forecasts of composite reflectivity and
43 accumulated precipitation in terms of the shape, location, and magnitude. However,
44 the AMV DA has difficulty in capturing the sharp moisture gradient associated with
45 the dryline and mostly underpredicts the associated scattered storms.

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Plain Language Summary

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The high-spatiotemporal-resolution Atmospheric Motion Vectors (AMVs) derived from newly launched GOES16/17 (also named GOES East/West) may have potential to improve short-range severe weather forecasts. However, this has not been extensively explored. In this study, a three-dimensional variational data assimilation scheme developed at NOAA/National Severe Storms Laboratory and the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model are used to study the impact of assimilation of GOES-R derived AMVs on short-range severe thunderstorm forecasts are evaluated. It is demonstrated that the short-range forecasts of the three severe weather events are all improved based on verification against radar reflectivity and precipitation observations when assimilating the AMV data.

59 **1. Introduction**

60 In Part I of this study, the impact of assimilating high-resolution AMVs on
61 convective-scale NWP was evaluated using simulated data of an idealized supercell
62 storm. The result of the baseline data assimilation (DA) experiment demonstrated that
63 the errors for wind and other model variables were reduced by assimilating the
64 simulated AMVs, leading to the enhancement of the storm-top divergence and
65 low-level convergence, and the low-level cold pool associated with the simulated
66 supercell storm. Three sets of sensitivity experiments were also performed to test the
67 impact of observation resolution, DA cycling frequency and horizontal correlation
68 length scale respectively. Overall, assimilating higher-spatial-resolution AMVs at
69 higher cycling frequency resulted in better initial conditions and storm forecasts,
70 except that the experiment with the most frequent DA cycling (5-min interval) tended
71 to overestimate temperature, nonprecipitating hydrometeor and storm relative helicity
72 fields, and may produce spurious cells in the short-term forecasts. It was also found
73 that the correlation length scale length of 20 km produced the best results for
74 assimilating the simulated AMV data. These conclusions will serve as a reference
75 guide for the assimilation of real-time AMV data.

76 The Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) aboard the GOES-16/17 (Schmit et al.,
77 2005, 2017) brings an opportunity for retrieving high spatiotemporal-resolution
78 AMVs over the Continental United States (CONUS), that can better monitor the
79 mesoscale or convective-scale atmospheric flow. However, the benefit of these data to
80 the convective scale NWP has not yet been extensively explored (Daniels et al., 2012).

81 Therefore in Part II of this research, the value of assimilating GOES-16 ABI derived
82 AMVs data on the high-impact weather events in a real scenario is assessed with the
83 same 3DVAR DA system used in Part I (Gao et al., 2004, 2013). Although the
84 encouraging results obtained in the idealized case study suggested that the simulated
85 high-resolution AMVs have a positive impact on convective-scale DA and storm
86 forecasts, the influence of the AMV observations in the real data cases may be
87 different depending on observation quality and distribution. As with the simulated
88 data, the AMVs are confined to the region and vertical layer where the targeted tracers
89 exist. There could be large areas without data, or there may be few data in the region
90 where more information about mesoscale and convective flows is needed. Acceptable
91 height range of AMVs and the corresponding data quality depends on the retrieving
92 band (Daniels et al., 2012), which should be considered in the quality control strategy.
93 Still, as demonstrated in Part I of this study, the storm morphology and evolution are
94 sensitive to the wind fields, the impact of AMV DA on severe storm forecasts can be
95 very useful depending on different weather situations.

96 Since the forecast model and the 3DVAR system have been described in part I
97 of this study, only the main points are briefly summarized and the refinement in the
98 quality control (QC) and assimilation settings for the GOES-16 derived AMVs, as
99 well as the experimental design, are presented in section 3. In section 4, results of the
100 three real data cases are discussed. Finally, the summary and conclusions are offered
101 in section 5.

102 **2. Brief description of GOES-16 AMV Data**

103 The post-processed AMVs in prepbuf format used in the operational models
104 contain wind observations at a much coarser spatial and temporal resolution, and
105 therefore are not suitable for convective scale NWP. As indicated in Part I, this study
106 uses the GOES-16 ABI Level 2 (L2) AMV product generated by NOAA NESDIS
107 Center for Satellite Applications and Research
108 ([https://www.bou.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/search?sub_id=0&datatype_family=GR](https://www.bou.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/search?sub_id=0&datatype_family=GRABIPRD&submit.x=15&submit.y=6)
109 [ABIPRD&submit.x=15&submit.y=6](https://www.bou.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/search?sub_id=0&datatype_family=GRABIPRD&submit.x=15&submit.y=6)) in NetCDF file format. The ABI aboard the
110 GOES-16/17 satellites offers 11 more bands and has four times the spatial resolution
111 and more than three times faster scanning ability than its predecessor on the GOES-N
112 series (Daniels et al., 2012; Goodman et al., 2012; Schmit et al., 2005, 2017). The
113 ABI AMV product is generated from a set of targeted tracers, including cloud edges
114 or moisture gradients, viewed separately in each of six selected spectral channels:
115 bands 2 (0.64 μm), 7 (3.9 μm), 8 (6.15 μm), 9 (7.0 μm), 10 (7.4 μm), and 14 (11.2 μm).
116 For the AMVs derived from band 8, both cloud and clear-sky water vapor based
117 product files are generated. Additionally, AMVs are retrieved for cloudy and
118 cloud-free, daylight and nightlight conditions depending on the band (Table 1). The
119 visible AMVs are only available during daytime while the AMVs from shortwave
120 infrared band 7 are produced during nighttime. Table 1 lists the band number, central
121 wavelength, tracer type, and temporal coverage for different ABI bands used to derive
122 AMVs.

123 *Table 1. List of the ABI bands used to derive AMVs. From left to right column, ABI*
124 *band number, central wavelength, tracer type, temporal coverage, and acceptable*
125 *height range.*

ABI Band	Central Wavelength (μm)	Tracer Type	Temporal coverage	Acceptable Height Range (hPa)
2	0.64	Cloud	Day	700 - 1000
7	3.9	Cloud	Night	700 - 1000
8	6.15	Cloud/ Clear-sky water vapor	Day and night	100 - 400
9	7.0	Clear-sky water vapor	Day and night	100 - 1000
10	7.4	Clear-sky water vapor	Day and night	450 - 700
14	11.2	Cloud	Day and night	100 - 1000

126 The ABI native spatial resolutions at nadir are 2 km for the infrared bands and
127 0.5 km for the 0.64-μm visible band. The spatial resolution of AMV data, which is
128 coarser than the ABI native spatial resolution, is determined by both the spatial and
129 temporal resolution of the ABI imagery and the scale of the intended feature being
130 tracked (Daniels et al., 2012; Hamada, 1983; Shenk, 1991). For example, the
131 horizontal resolution of the visible AMVs (derived from visible band 2) is 7.5 km,
132 while the resolution of the wind data from the water vapor bands (band 8, 9, 10) and
133 long wave infrared band (band 14) are 30 km and 38 km, respectively (Daniels et al.,
134 2012). To account for the error in AMV height assignment in the retrieving algorithm,
135 the vertical resolution of AMV product is quite sparse, with just three layers: 1000–
136 700 hPa, 700–400 hPa, and 400–100 hPa (Rao et al., 2002). And the acceptable height
137 range of AMVs depends on the retrieving band (Table 1). Most studies show that the
138 vertical distribution of the multispectral winds exhibits a typical bimodal pattern with
139 maximums in the upper and lower troposphere, which is determined by the nature of
140 the derivation algorithm (Goerss et al., 1998; Lean & Bormann, 2019; Nebuda et al.,

141 2014; Xiao et al., 2002). Moreover, assigning a height to the targeted tracer is often
142 considered to be the major uncertainty for AMVs (C. S. Velden & Bedka, 2009).
143 Some research estimated the AMVs height assignment error and concluded that it is
144 the largest in the middle level (700-400 hPa) and smallest in the upper level (400-100
145 hPa) (Lean & Bormann, 2019; Salonen et al., 2015).

146 In terms of the temporal resolution, the GOES-16 AMVs are available once an
147 hour for the Full Disk (FD) of the Earth, every 15 minutes over the CONUS region,
148 and every 5 minutes over a selectable 1000 by 1000 km mesoscale sector box
149 (MESO). Following the conclusions from DA cycling frequency sensitivity
150 experiment in Part I, the 15-min AMV data over the CONUS scan sector is chosen to
151 be assimilated in this study. Owing to higher temporal, spatial and spectral resolution,
152 as well as increased radiometric performance of the GOES-16 ABI, the retrieval
153 algorithm is improved in the presence of better target selection, feature tracking, and
154 target height assignment, resulting in higher quality AMV observations as a better
155 representation of the low-level visible winds over land (Daniels et al., 2012; Lean &
156 Bormann, 2019). Therefore, it is expected that assimilating the
157 high-spatiotemporal-resolution AMVs will introduce mesoscale or convective-scale
158 airflow features into analysis and consequently improve the accuracy of severe storm
159 forecasts over CONUS.

160 **3. Forecast Model, Data Quality Control, and Experimental Design**

161 3.1 Forecast Model

162 The forecast model used in this study is the fully compressible, nonhydrostatic

163 Advanced Research version of the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF-ARW)
164 Model version 3.6.1 (Skamarock et al., 2008). The DA and forecast experiments are
165 performed on one single domain with a horizontal spatial resolution of 1.5 km and
166 horizontal dimensions of 600×600 grid points. The simulation domains from the
167 Warn-on-Forecast System (WoFS) real-time Spring Forecast Experiment (SFE) runs
168 are employed for all three cases in this study (Junjun Hu et al., 2020). There are 51
169 stretched vertical levels up with a model top set at 20-hPa. For the physical
170 parameterizations, we select the NSSL 2-moment 4-ice category bulk microphysics
171 scheme (Mansell et al., 2010; Mansell & Ziegler, 2013; Ziegler, 1985), the Rapid
172 Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM) longwave radiation scheme (Mlawer et al., 1997),
173 the Dudhia shortwave radiation scheme (Dudhia, 1989), the Rapid Update Cycle
174 (RUC) land surface scheme (Benjamin et al., 2004) , and the Yonsei University (YSU)
175 planetary boundary layer scheme (Hong et al., 2006).

176 3.2 Data Quality Control and Assimilation Setting

177 Following Part I of this paper, this work employs the NSSL Experimental WoF
178 3DVAR system (NSSL3DVAR; Gao et al., 2013, 2016; Gao & Stensrud, 2012, 2014).
179 The NSSL3DVAR system is capable of effectively assimilating radar reflectivity,
180 radial velocity, satellite-derived cloud water path and total precipitable water,
181 Geostationary Lightning Mapper Lightning (GLM)-derived water vapor, sounding,
182 and surface data (Fierro et al., 2019; J. Hu et al., 2019; Junjun Hu et al., 2020; Lai et
183 al., 2019; Pan et al., 2018). In this research, the QC and assimilation modules for the
184 GOES-16 AMVs are built into the NSSL3DVAR system, which will be described in

185 more detail later in this section.

186 As mentioned above, this work assimilates ABI L2 AMV data from GOES-16
187 over the CONUS region. The raw observations of wind speed and azimuth from the
188 AMV datasets were converted to zonal and meridional wind components (u and v)
189 before entering the NSSL3DVAR system. In order to make full use of the mesoscale
190 and convective-scale airflow information, data thinning for AMVs is not employed in
191 this study. The wind observations are passed through a QC module to filter out bad
192 data, prior to their insertion into the analysis procedure. Based on the
193 channel-dependent pressure ranges for AMVs (Daniels et al., 2012) and the QC
194 strategy adopted by previous studies (Kim et al., 2017; Lim et al., 2019; Mallick &
195 Jones, 2020; Sawada et al., 2019; C. Velden et al., 2017), the 7-step observation
196 checks depending on retrieval band are applied as the following:

- 197 (1) Remove all the wind data with a pressure height greater than 950 hPa or less
198 than 100 hPa;
- 199 (2) For the winds derived from both visible (0.64 μm) and shortwave infrared
200 (3.9 μm) bands, remove data with pressure height above 750 hPa;
- 201 (3) For the upper-level water vapor winds (6.15 μm), reject data with a pressure
202 height greater than 400 hPa;
- 203 (4) For band 9 (7.0 μm) winds, only keep the data with pressure height above
204 450 hPa and with the minimum wind speed threshold of 8 m/s;
- 205 (5) For the longwave infrared band (11.2 μm), remove winds retrieved between
206 800-400 hPa;

- 207 (6) Reject all the data with a solar zenith angle larger than 68 degrees;
- 208 (7) A relaxed gross error check, which is to increase the retention of winds
- 209 representing smaller-scale flow, is performed to eliminate the observations
- 210 outside of set tolerances from the interpolated model background field.

211 The above QC checks generally filter out 20-30% of the available AMV

212 observations in each analysis cycle. As in Part I of this paper, the observation and

213 background error for wind components are set to be 6 m/s and 3-6 m/s, respectively.

214 This study adopts the minimization process in two loops, each with a prescribed

215 horizontal and vertical correlation scale for the recursive filter used in the program

216 (Gao et al., 2004; Purser et al., 2003). The correlation scales determine how far the

217 observation information will spread in model space. Following the sensitivity

218 experiment results in Part I, the horizontal correlation scale lengths are set to be 50

219 km in the first loop and 20 km in the second loop. And the corresponding vertical

220 correlation lengths are 7 and 5 grid points, respectively.

221 3.3 Experimental Design

222 The assimilation of GOES-16 ABI L2 AMV data is performed with three

223 high-impact weather events that occurred over the Great Plains of the United States in

224 spring 2018 and 2019. The DA and forecast cycle workflow, similar to that of WoFS

225 real-time SFE runs (Junjun Hu et al., 2020; Jones et al., 2018), is utilized for each real

226 case (Fig. 1). The WRF model is initialized with the 3-km High Resolution Rapid

227 Refresh (HRRR) forecast product at 1800 UTC, which is downscaled onto the 1.5-km

228 grid. Then the AMV DA is cycled from 1800 UTC to 0300 UTC at 15-min intervals,

229 with a 3-h free forecast launched every hour starting from 1900 UTC. The GOES-16
 230 AMV data passing all QC checks between $t-10\text{min}$ and $t+5\text{min}$ are accumulated and
 231 assimilated at each analysis time t . A control run (denoted as NoDA) is also
 232 performed by integrating the model forward without assimilating any observation and
 233 is compared to the AMV DA experiment (referred to as AMV).

GOES-16 AMV data are assimilated at 15-min interval

234
 235 *Figure 1. Illustration of the data assimilation and forecast cycle workflow. A 3-h*
 236 *forecast is launched every hour from 1900 to 0300 UTC (namely, nine separate*
 237 *forecasts).*

238 To obtain both qualitative and quantitative evaluations of the AMV DA impact
 239 on the analyses and forecasts, the model reflectivity and precipitation fields are
 240 verified against the composite radar reflectivity observations from the NSSL
 241 Multi-Radar Multi-Sensor (MRMS) product (Smith et al., 2016) and the Stage IV
 242 hourly rainfall estimates from the National Centers for Environmental Prediction
 243 (Baldwin & Mitchell, 1997), all of which are interpolated onto the 1.5-km model grids
 244 for the convenience of comparing observations to model simulations. Specifically, the
 245 verification parameters include the probability of detection (POD), the false alarm rate
 246 (FAR), success ratio (SR), and critical success index (CSI), and neighborhood-based
 247 scores like the equitable threat scores (ETS; Clark et al., 2010) and the fractions skill

248 scores (FSS; Roberts & Lean, 2008).

249 **4. Results**

250 The three high-impact weather events that occurred over the Great Plains of the
251 United States on 1 May 2018, 28 May 2019, and 17 May 2019 produced distinct
252 storm modes under different weather situations. Numerous severe weather warnings
253 were issued by the National Weather Service (NWS) for all three cases with
254 subsequent storm reports including large hail, damaging wind, and tornadoes. In
255 addition to the wind and equivalent potential temperature analyses, the short-term (0–
256 3 h) forecasts of composite reflectivity and accumulated precipitation are discussed.

257 4.1 Case 1: 1 May 2018

258 During the late afternoon and the evening of 1 May 2018, a southwest-northeast
259 slow-moving cold front arcing across west-central Kansas into eastern Nebraska
260 moved northeastward with a surface low over Kansas. Owing to the favorable
261 environmental conditions, clustered storms developed near the low pressure and along
262 the front through the night and finally merged into a quasi-linear convective system,
263 squall line (not shown). Between 2300 UTC 1 May and 0200 UTC 2 May, a total of
264 13 tornadoes and several large hail and damaging wind events were reported in
265 Kansas, Nebraska, and Oklahoma. Moreover, a couple of discrete storms initiated
266 along a dryline extending southward from the front.

267

268 *Figure 2. The geographical distribution of the GOES-16 AMV observations which are*
 269 *assimilated at (a) 1800 UTC 1 May, (b) 2100 UTC 1 May, (c) 0000 UTC 2 May and*
 270 *(d) 0300 UTC 2 May 2018. Red barbs represent AMVs within the 1000–700 hPa layer,*
 271 *blue AMV barbs are within the 700–400 hPa layer, and green AMV barbs are within*
 272 *the 400–100 hPa layer.*

273

274 Figs. 2a-d display the geographical distribution of AMV data assimilated at
 275 1800 UTC and 2100 UTC 1 May as well as 0000 UTC and 0300 UTC 2 May 2018. It
 276 is seen that AMVs within the 400–100 hPa layer greatly outnumber the wind vectors
 277 below 400 hPa. This occurs because the majority of winds are retrieved from the
 278 upper-level water vapor band (6.15 μ m) which represents upper-level cirrus cloud
 279 movements. A few AMVs from longwave infrared band (11.2 μ m) are also derived
 within this layer. Diffluent flow within the 400–100 hPa layer is apparent at the

280 periphery of the squall line as it moved northeastward (Figs. 2b-d). The
281 upper-tropospheric divergence signature is a good measure of the updraft velocity and
282 plays an important role in initiating convective storm development and maintaining
283 storm intensity (Doswell, 2001). The low-level cyclonic wind shear behind the cold
284 front is evident within the 1000–700 hPa layer over the central Nebraska (Fig. 2c).

285 To assess how the AMV DA impacts the mesoscale airflow, the wind analyses
286 and the associated divergence field are examined first (Fig. 3). The reason for
287 selecting 2300 UTC 1 May 2018 is that the squall line along the front has been
288 developing into a mature stage until this time and the cumulative benefit from the
289 prior analysis and forecast cycles is also relatively perceptible. The 850-hPa wind and
290 equivalent potential temperature analyses show that the front and dryline boundaries
291 (indicated by the blue thick line in Fig. 3a) in NoDA are basically aligned along a line,
292 while the AMV experiment produces a turning point, which is the intersection
293 between a more west-east oriented front and a dryline slightly farther to the western
294 Kansas (Fig. 3a vs Fig. 3b). The cyclonic rotation associated with the low over the
295 north Kansas and central Nebraska is slightly enhanced by AMV. And the upper-level
296 divergent flows above the cold pools are more pronounced in AMV than those in
297 NoDA (Fig. 3c vs Fig. 3d). It is evident that the pattern of the upper-level divergence
298 field in AMV corresponds better to the area of > 30 dBZ observed reflectivity and the
299 corresponding magnitude is also improved by AMV (Fig. 3e vs Fig. 3f).

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301

302 *Figure 3. (a)-(b) 850-hPa and (c)-(d) 200-hPa wind analyses ($m s^{-1}$, vectors) with*
 303 *850-hPa equivalent potential temperature (K) indicated in colors for (left) NoDA and*
 304 *(right) AMV experiments at 2300 UTC 1 May 2018. (e)-(f) 200-hPa divergence*
 305 *analyses ($10^{-5} s^{-1}$, shaded) for (left) NoDA and (right) AMV experiments. The contours*
 306 *in (e) and (f) represent the MRMS composite reflectivity at 30 and 50 dBZ.*

307

308 *Figure 4. The composite reflectivity (dBZ, shaded) for (a)–(c) MRMS observations*
 309 *interpolated onto the 1.5 km simulation domain, (d)–(f) NoDA, and (g)–(i) AMV*
 310 *experiments at (left, 1-h forecast) 0000 UTC 2 May, (middle, 2-h forecast) 0100 UTC*
 311 *2 May, and (right, 3-h forecast) 0200 UTC 2 May 2018.*

312 The 1-3 h forecasts of composite reflectivity fields are illustrated in Fig. 4 for
 313 the NoDA and AMV experiments together with the MRMS observations. The
 314 quasi-linear convective system develops along the cold front as well as the discrete
 315 storm cells initiated near the dryline (Figs. 4a-c). NoDA produces two major
 316 separated areas of precipitation, more similar to two mesoscale convective systems
 317 (MCS), instead of a linear system over northeast Kansas and southwest Iowa (Figs.

318 4d-f). In contrast, the storms in the AMV experiment show a more linear convective
319 mode, especially for the first hour forecast, and they are comparable to the MRMS
320 observations in terms of shape and location, although individual cells are not perfectly
321 captured (Figs. 4g-i). This indicates that the assimilation of high-resolution AMV data
322 can improve the storm development and movement near the frontal boundary by
323 providing a better representation of storm wind information. However, the discrete
324 cells over the south Kansas are either missed or predicted further southward in the
325 AMV experiment. This occurs because an isolated cell or a smaller cluster of cells
326 may be difficult for the AMV data to discern by nature. Furthermore, the hourly
327 accumulated precipitation (APCP) fields from NoDA and AMV are also compared in
328 Fig. 5. Along the quasi-linear convective system, the areal coverage of hourly APCP
329 < 20 mm is generally improved by the AMV DA. However, both NoDA and AMV
330 appear to mostly overpredict the precipitation amount associated with some cells
331 embedded within the linear system. Specifically, AMV overpredicts the 1-h forecast
332 precipitation over north Kansas and it underpredicts the rainfall over western Iowa for
333 the 2-h to 3-h forecasts (Figs. 5g-i vs Figs. 5a-c).

334

335 *Figure 5. The 1-h accumulated precipitation (APCP) fields (mm, shaded) for (a)–(c)*
 336 *from the Stage IV multi-sensor rainfall estimates, (d)–(f) NoDA, and (g)–(i) AMV*
 337 *experiment at (left, 1-h forecast) 0000 UTC 2 May, (middle, 2-h forecast) 0100 UTC 2*
 338 *May, and (right, 3-h forecast) 0200 UTC 2 May 2018.*

339 To quantify the performance of the composite reflectivity and APCP forecasts
 340 for the AMV DA, the categorical performance diagrams and the neighborhood-based
 341 ETS are computed and aggregated over nine 3-h free forecasts launched every hour
 342 from 1900 UTC to 0300 UTC. The performance diagram efficiently combines the
 343 information derived from key contingency table elements including POD, SR (1 –
 344 FAR), and CSI (Roebber, 2009). The closer the values of POD, SR, and CSI approach

345

346 *Figure 6. Aggregate score metrics of composite reflectivity fields relative to MRMS*
 347 *observations for nine 3-hour free forecasts for the NoDA (black) and AMV (red)*
 348 *experiments in Case 1. (a)-(c) show the performance diagrams at 1-h, 2-h, and 3-h*
 349 *forecast time, and (d)-(f) the equitable threat score (ETS) for (left) 30 dBZ, (middle)*
 350 *40 dBZ, and (right) 50 dBZ thresholds, respectively. Results are shown for a*
 351 *neighborhood radius of 12-km.*

352 unity, the better forecast is achieved, with the perfect forecast located at the
 353 upper-right corner of the diagram. All the score metrics are calculated for a
 354 neighborhood radius of 12 km. The ETS for composite reflectivity is computed at
 355 15-min intervals and that for APCP is at hourly intervals. As the composite
 356 reflectivity threshold increases from 30 dBZ to 50 dBZ, the forecast skill drops
 357 dramatically for the NoDA and AMV experiments, owing to decreased PODs along
 358 with increased FARs (Figs. 6a-c). Nevertheless, AMV consistently outperforms
 359 NoDA at all thresholds for each forecast lead time, with higher POD, SR, CSI, and
 360 ETS values. It is also worth noting that the positive impact of AMV DA becomes

361 slightly larger when the reflectivity threshold increases from 30 to 50 dBZ. Similar
 362 trends and behavior are obtained in the performance diagrams and ETS figures for the
 363 hourly APCP against NCEP Stage IV multisensory rainfall product, highlighting the
 364 superior performance of AMV (Fig. 7). In terms of the 1-h and 3-h score metrics in
 365 the performance diagrams, AMV substantially corrects the significant high bias (black
 366 dots closer to the upper-left corner of the diagram) and slightly increases the CSI
 367 values, while it generates lower PODs at the same time (Figs. 7a-c). One potential
 368 explanation is that the more linear convective mode of APCP forecast with AMV
 369 effectively reduces the false alarms with a narrower areal coverage of APCP > 20 mm
 370 (Fig. 5). Combined with the inability of the AMV data to resolve individual cells,
 371 lower POD values are obtained.

372
 373 *Figure 7. Same as in Figure 6, but for hourly APCP relative to Stage IV rainfall*
 374 *estimates calculated using the following thresholds: (a) and (d) 2.5 mm, (b) and (e) 5*
 375 *mm, and (c) and (f) 10mm.*

376 4.2 Case 2: 28 May 2019

377 On the morning of 28 May 2019, a cluster of elevated thunderstorms initiated in
378 central Kansas, from which the convective outflow reinforced the west-east front
379 across northeast Kansas and northern Missouri. After the elevated convection began
380 to interact with the baroclinic zone in northeast Kansas, it grew upscale by late
381 afternoon into a MCS that spread northeast across northern Missouri and southern
382 Iowa. Meanwhile, a weak surface cyclone in north-central Kansas moved
383 east-northeastward toward Missouri with a trailing cold front shifting slowly
384 southeastward (Figs. 10a, b, c). To the south of the cyclone, a dryline sharpened
385 across western Oklahoma and northwest Texas. These surface boundaries provided
386 the primary foci for severe thunderstorm development. Between 2300 UTC 28 May
387 and 0200 UTC 29 May, a total of 19 tornadoes and several large hail and damaging
388 wind events were reported in Kansas, Missouri, and Oklahoma. An EF-2 tornado was
389 confirmed in Clay County of Missouri around 0100 UTC 29 May by the NWS
390 damage survey team, with a maximum wind of 51.4 m/s and a maximum width of 365
391 m. Hail up to baseball size (2.75 inch) was reported in Trego County of Kansas and as
392 large as tea cup size (3 inch) in Gove County of Kansas.

393 In the early 3DVAR cycles for this case, most AMV observations are derived
394 from the visible band within the 1000–700 hPa layer, by the means of tracking
395 immature, nonprecipitating cumulus (Bedka & Mecikalski, 2005). As the front moved
396 east-northeastward, the associated low-level jet transported the moist and unstable
397 airmass across the warm sector (Figs. 8a-e). During the later cycles (Figs. 8f-i), the

398 AMVs generally represent the flow aloft within the 400–100 hPa layer and most
399 winds are retrieved from the longwave infrared band (11.2 μ m). The lack of AMVs in
400 the mid-layer (700–400 hPa) for both cases (case 1 and case 2) is due to the nature of
401 the AMV retrieval algorithm. Since the retrieved AMVs show larger errors between
402 700 and 400 hPa (Sears & Velden, 2012; C. Velden et al., 2017), the longwave
403 infrared winds within this layer are excluded by the QC procedures.

404

405 *Figure 8. Same as Fig. 2, but for the AMV observations from 1800 UTC 28 May to*
406 *0200 UTC 29 May 2019 at 1-h intervals.*

407

408

Figure 9. Same as Fig. 3, but for the analyses at 2300 UTC 28 May 2019.

409

The analyzed potential temperature and wind fields are examined in Fig. 9 as

410

before. Comparison of Fig. 9a against Fig. 9b reveals that the AMV experiment

411 successfully captures the west-east front near the Missouri-Iowa state-line, while the
412 front in NoDA extends too far northeastward into central Iowa (indicated by the blue
413 thick lines in Figs. 9a-b). Consistent with the 850-hPa temperature and wind analyses,
414 the 200-hPa divergent flows are widely evident above the cold pools associated with
415 the MCS along the front and the isolated storms over eastern Kansas and northeastern
416 Oklahoma (Figs. 9c-d). Evaluated against the observed composite reflectivity (area of >
417 30 dBZ in Figs. 9e-f), NoDA produces a distinctive northward bias in the upper-level
418 divergence field over south-central Iowa, while AMV alleviates this displacement
419 error (Fig. 9e vs Fig. 9f). Additionally, AMV also yields approximately comparable
420 divergence cores matched with several discrete storms in the area of > 30 dBZ
421 reflectivity, except for the thin line across the northeastern state border of Oklahoma
422 (Fig. 9f).

423 Owing to a better representation of the thermodynamic environment, AMV
424 reasonably reproduces the MCS across the northern Missouri and southern Iowa in
425 terms of location and intensity, correcting the notable slower and northward
426 propagation bias in the NoDA storm forecast (Fig. 10). As is seen, both NoDA and
427 AMV underpredict the widely scattered storms farther south along the dryline. This
428 occurs because AMV DA does not help reduce the analysis errors for the variables not
429 directly related to wind observations, such as humidity, which is also indicated by the
430 idealized experiments in Part I of this study. Therefore, similar to NoDA, the AMV
431 experiment still underestimates the sharp humidity gradient along the dryline (not
432 shown). Consistent with the reflectivity forecasts, AMV improves the areal coverage

433 of 1-3 h ACP forecasts across the Missouri-Iowa border with somewhat larger or
 434 smaller rainfall amounts compared to observations, especially for general better
 435 rainfall position and cell alignment in the first 2 hours (Fig. 11).

436
 437 *Figure 10. Same as Fig. 4, but for (left, analysis time) 2300 UTC 28 May, (middle, 1-h*
 438 *forecast) 0000 UTC 29 May, and (right, 2-h forecast) 0100 UTC 29 May 2019.*

439 From the aggregate forecast statistics for composite reflectivity, the
 440 improvements of ETS and CSI by AMV over NoDA persist through the 1-3 h
 441 forecasts, although the difference between them decreases for later forecasts (Fig. 12).
 442 For the 30- and 40-dBZ thresholds, the higher forecast skill produced by AMV is

443 largely due to an increased POD, with SR being approximately constant or slightly
 444 smaller (Figs. 12a-b). At 50 dBZ, however, AMV produces higher POD and SR,
 445 which is more notable during the first two hours (Fig. 12c). In terms of APCP, AMV

446
 447 *Figure 11. Same as Fig. 5, but for (left, 1-h forecast) 0000 UTC 29 May, (middle, 2-h*
 448 *forecast) 0100 UTC 29 May, and (right, 3-h forecast) 0200 UTC 29 May 2019.*

449 tends to show overall larger values of SR and CSI but smaller PODs (Figs. 13a-c). For
 450 all APCP thresholds, AMV persistently produces larger ETS at 3-h forecasts although
 451 being small (e.g. < 0.3 at 10mm) and not significantly outperforming NoDA (Figs.
 452 13d-f).

453
454

Figure 12. Same as Fig. 6, but for Case 2.

455
456

Figure 13. Same as Fig. 7, but for Case 2.

457 4.3 Case 3: 17 May 2019

458 Through 17 May 2019 afternoon and evening, an intensifying High Plains

459 surface low moved northeastward out of Colorado across Nebraska, along with an
460 eastward shifting upper-level trough. This contributed to a pronounced jet streak in
461 the low- and mid-troposphere and favorable deep-layer shear for organized storms
462 across the western-central Nebraska, where multiple tornadoes and hail events were
463 reported. A warm front extended eastward from the surface low, and transitioned into
464 a cold front across the Ohio Valley/mid-Atlantic. In addition, a dryline was present
465 across western Kansas where several storms developed causing several tornadoes and
466 very large hail owing to the favorable large-scale environment.

467 Fig. 14 highlights how the AMV DA benefits the storm wind environment as
468 well as the thermodynamic analyses through the successive model adjustments to the
469 background fields from the prior analysis cycles. NoDA underestimates the sharp
470 temperature gradient associated with the front boundary across northwestern Nebraska
471 (indicated by the blue thick line in Fig. 14b) while the AMV experiment successfully
472 captures it with stronger low-level warm advection and cold surge on west side of the
473 front. Discrete storms developed near surface low at the intersection of the front and
474 dryline and eventually organized into a linear mode spreading northeast through the
475 destabilizing warm sector (Figs. 15a-c). Comparison of Figs. 15d-f against Figs. 15a-c
476 reveals that a faster and eastward movement bias is present over Nebraska in the
477 NoDA storm forecasts. Owing to the more favorable storm environment (Fig. 14b),
478 the AMV experiment yields approximately comparable quasi-linear deep convection
479 evolving across the western Nebraska with slightly weaker bias (Figs. 15 g-i).
480 However, light spurious stratiform precipitation widely occurred across eastern

482

483 *Figure 14. 700-hPa wind analyses ($m s^{-1}$, vectors) with (a)-(b) equivalent potential*
 484 *temperature (K), and (c)-(d) water vapor mixing ratio ($g kg^{-1}$) indicated in colors for*
 485 *(left) NoDA and (right) AMV experiments at 0100 UTC 18 May 2019.*

486 in the 3-h forecast (Fig. 15i). It is also seen that both AMV and NoDA fail to simulate

487 the isolated cells initiated farther south along the dryline across western Kansas. This

488 is because neither experiment reproduces such a sharp humidity gradient in this region,

489 with the moisture gradient in AMV even slightly weaker (Figs. 14c-d). The humidity

490 gradient is crucial to the dryline, which is defined simply as a sharp boundary between

491 moist air and dry air. As expected, the AMV experiment generally improves the areal
 492 coverage of 1-3 h APCP forecasts across the west-central Nebraska, in spite of the
 493 bias in the rainfall amount (Fig. 16). However, it misses the precipitation associated
 494 with the dryline in western Kansas.

495

496 *Figure 15. Same as Fig. 4, but for (left, analysis time) 0100 UTC 18 May, (middle, 1-h*
 497 *forecast) 0200 UTC 18 May, and (right, 2-h forecast) 0300 UTC 18 May, 2019.*

498 Similar to the results discussed in previous cases, aggregate forecast statistics for
 499 nine separate 3-h forecasts are computed to provide a more comprehensive view of
 500 the AMV DA impact. For the 1-3 h reflectivity forecasts, AMV shows an

501 overwhelming superiority over NoDA with much higher POD, CSI, SR, and ETS at
 502 all the thresholds (Fig. 17). The weaker bias in reflectivity forecasts (Fig. 15) results
 503 in overall small values of POD and ETS at 50 dBZ (Figs. 17c, f). In terms of APCP,
 504 AMV exhibits notably less false alarms and larger CSI but smaller POD values at 1-h
 505 and 3-h forecasts (Figs. 18a-c). For the 2.5-mm threshold, the improvement of ETS by
 506 AMV over NoDA persists through the 1-3 h forecasts (Fig. 18d). At 5- and 10-mm,
 507 AMV has lower ETS for the 1-h forecast but then surpasses NoDA (Figs. 18e-f).

508

509 *Figure 16. Same as Fig. 5, but for (left, 1-h forecast) 0200 UTC 18 May, (middle, 2-h*
 510 *forecast) 0300 UTC 18 May, and (right, 3-h forecast) 0400 UTC 18 May, 2019.*

511
512

Figure 17. Same as Fig. 6, but Case 3.

513
514

Figure 18. Same as in Figure 7, but for Case 3.

515 **5. Summary and conclusions**

516 This study investigates the impact of assimilating GOES-16 derived AMV

517 observations using the NSSL 3DVAR system and WRF model on the short-term
518 severe weather forecasts. The assessment of the AMV DA performance is carried out
519 with three high-impact weather events that occurred in spring 2018 and 2019 over the
520 Great Plains of the United States. First, the lower- and upper-level wind analyses and
521 the associated divergence field and potential temperature fields are examined for each
522 case. Then the short-term forecasts of composite reflectivity and hourly APCP are
523 quantitatively verified against the MRMS and Stage IV products in the form of
524 performance diagrams and ETS values.

525 The vertical distribution of the AMV observations available for assimilation in
526 each case varies with the derivation channels used to track cloud or clear-sky water
527 vapor under different atmospheric conditions. The results from the three convective
528 events exhibit a bimodal pattern with maximum AMV number in the upper (400–100
529 hPa) and lower (1000–700 hPa) troposphere, that is similar to many earlier AMV DA
530 studies. The lack of AMVs in the mid-layer (700–400 hPa) is determined by the
531 nature of the retrieval algorithm.

532 The wind analyses for the large-scale environment and mesoscale convective
533 systems are improved by the assimilation of GOES-16 AMVs. The upper-level
534 divergence associated with the deep convection is also enhanced. Moreover, the AMV
535 DA benefits the equivalent potential temperature fields through the successive
536 adjustments during the model integration from the prior 3DVAR analysis cycles.
537 These improvements lead to the better simulation of the location and shape for the
538 boundaries including fronts and cyclones, that influences the subsequent storm

539 evolution and movement. For the quasi-linear or MCS along the boundaries, the AMV
540 DA outperforms NoDA by yielding more reasonable short-term (0–3 h) forecasts of
541 composite reflectivity and accumulated precipitation in terms of their shape, location,
542 and magnitude. Overall, the aggregate forecast statistics indicate the positive impact
543 of AMV DA on reflectivity and APCP forecasts, although the trends of POD and SR
544 forecasts seem to be case dependent. However, the AMV DA has difficulty in
545 capturing the sharp moisture gradient associated with the dryline and generally
546 underpredicts the associated scattered storms. This is because AMV DA has difficulty
547 in reducing the analysis errors for the variables not directly related with wind
548 observations, such as humidity. Given the spatial resolution of the current GOES-16
549 AMV product, the isolated cells or quite small cluster of cells may not be discernable
550 by the AMV data.

551 Although this study shows the usefulness of the high-resolution GOES-16 AMV
552 data for improving convective-scale short-term forecasts, more issues related to the
553 AMV DA should be addressed in future. Due to the complexity in estimating AMVs
554 errors, further research will be devoted at refining the observation error estimation and
555 quality control. The application of the AMV DA to different phases in a life cycle of a
556 convective storm will also be tested. For example, the AMVs prior to the cumulus
557 stage could be separately assimilated to assess its impact on convection initiation in
558 the unstable atmosphere. Considering the limitation of AMVs in adjusting the model
559 moisture field, other available high-resolution observations, such as radar radial
560 velocity and reflectivity, satellite-derived cloud water path and total precipitable water

561 data, could be effectively assimilated together with AMVs in future work to better
562 depict the near-storm environment. It is possible that assimilating radar radial velocity
563 data combined with AMV DA can make up for their respective observation gaps. So
564 as a next step, the impact of assimilating both radial velocity and AMV data on the
565 convective-scale NWP, especially for the storm structure forecast and isolated cell
566 initiation, will be investigated in the near future.

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574 **Data Availability Statement**

575 The NSSL 3DVAR system is available upon request under appropriate research
576 agreement through the National Severe Storm Laboratory/NOAA. The WRF model is
577 available at: <https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf-release-information>.

578

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